

Bound states of Weyl fermions

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Abstract

I apply a recently developed technique for bound states [1] to pairs of Weyl fermions. Here, the focus is on the example of pairing left-handed to conjugates of right-handed particles, which under circumstances described below, create mass terms for a transition to a Dirac equation for the constituent particles. The technique results in a bosonic theory for the bound system, which can develop a non-trivial saddle point with a massive and a massless excitation modes. The non-trivial saddle point is a feature of the functional approach, which is not present in the original Bethe-Salpeter equation [2].

1 Introduction

Why study bound states of Weyl fermions? Firstly, if the known elementary fermions are stripped off their mass, they all obey the same Weyl equation. Weyl fermions have no other internal structure than their spin of one-half and their handedness. Textbooks tell us that in the early universe, before any symmetry breaking had set in, there were no differences between quarks and leptons [3]. Fermions without mass and with the same coupling to intermediary vector fields (before symmetry breaking) obey the same Weyl equation. Any differentiation would be merely by labels, not by differences in parameters. Only the introduction of masses and couplings to other fields lead to different configurations. In that sense Weyl fermions are generic building blocks for all fermions.

If bound states between Weyl fermions exist, which by no means is clear, the technique developed in [1] implies a bosonic field with potential term and an approximate Yukawa-type coupling with the constituent fermions. In a sense, they carry their own symmetry breaking field. The necessary non-linear field terms extend the original Bethe-Salpeter approach [2]. If the potential develops a non-trivial saddle point corresponding to a condensate, this introduces a mass to the boson and implicitly to the fermionic constituent excitations. Different eigenstates of the bound system lead to different masses. This means that bound states are one way to give fermions additional structure that distinguishes one from the other.

The focus of this study is to investigate the method for a more specific, yet generic setting. I detail out the saddle point equation and the Gaussian approximation in order to see whether such condensates can exist and what structure the bound state action develops. This program should pave the way for future work considering explicit interactions and explicit types of fermions.

Indeed it can be verified that the quadratic and quartic expansion terms have different signs and an attractive force can lead to a condensate. From spin algebra, one might expect that a pair of Weyl fermions results in a spin-0 boson (singlet) and a spin-1 boson (triplet). Although this is mostly correct, at the trivial saddle point only the maximum spin configurations (i.e., spins plus one and minus one) survive the path integral. If there is a condensate, there is a massless and a massive

mode. I.e., a two or more component field emerges naturally. It then depends on the existence of a gauge field able to remove the massless term or not. Otherwise massless modes survive. Formally, the theory takes a shape slightly different from a Klein-Gordon equation with a fourth-order contact interaction. One advantage is that the free equation of motion is of Schroedinger type. However, projectors are involved.

Bound states in quantum field theory are less main stream as scattering theory, but they can give valuable information about the interaction. The set of known gauge fields contains attractive forces, because there are bound states. Baryons, mesons, atoms are just a few examples. In contrast, scattering experiments with particles interaction via a force with coupling constant g often only probe orders of g^{2n} , such that it is not clear whether a force is attractive or repulsive. Bound states and condensates are two ways to reveal attractive forces.

2 Choice of Weyl fermion pairs

The type of binding in this work aims at a coupling of left-handed and right-handed components in a form as it occurs in the Dirac equation. Weyl fermions obey the massless limit of the Dirac equation, which takes a particularly simple form in the Weyl representation. I will use a convention for the Weyl representation, in which the upper two components correspond to right-handed fermions and the lower two components to the left-handed fermions [4]. The Weyl equations follow from the $m \rightarrow 0$ limit of the Dirac equation in the Weyl representation:

$$i\partial_t\Psi = \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p} & -m\mathbb{1} \\ -m\mathbb{1} & -\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p} \end{pmatrix} \Psi, \quad \text{with } \Psi \xrightarrow{m \rightarrow 0} \begin{pmatrix} u_R \\ u_L \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

Before sending the mass term to zero, bispinors u_R and u_L would not be fully appropriate as the coupling destroys a strict handedness. Thus the limit notation. Having stated this once, I will not make the distinction below.

For massless Weyl fermions the free starting action is

$$S = \int d^4x u_R^\dagger [i\partial_t - \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p}] u_R + \int d^4x u_L^\dagger [i\partial_t + \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p}] u_L, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{p} is the momentum operator, and so the partition function becomes

$$Z = \int \mathcal{D}u_R^\dagger \mathcal{D}u_R \mathcal{D}u_L^\dagger \mathcal{D}u_L e^{iS[u_R^\dagger, u_R, u_L^\dagger, u_L]}. \quad (3)$$

The mass terms in an action for Dirac fermions, before taking the limit $m \rightarrow 0$, would be

$$S_m = \int d^4x u_R^\dagger m\mathbb{1}u_L + \int d^4x u_L^\dagger m\mathbb{1}u_R. \quad (4)$$

Note that we can exchange the role of left- and right-handed particles anytime by the transformation $\mathbf{p} \rightarrow -\mathbf{p}$ (while for the time-like component $\omega \rightarrow \omega$).

We then add an interaction, typically a gauge interaction via minimal coupling, but there is no need to restrict the explicit functional form for the moment. Some options will be discussed below.

The technique described in [1] allows to formally pair particles without much restriction and so we can apply it to the special case of Weyl fermions. However, the existence of pairs of Weyl fermions hinges on the existence of a non-trivial bound state saddle point, or at least the ability of

capturing resonances in the vicinity of a trivial saddle point. More on these questions will follow further below. Here, we intend to do the pairing such that the coupling to coexisting unbound fermions is of the mass type, analogous to Eq. (4) i.e.,

$$u_R^\dagger \Lambda u_L + u_L^\dagger \Lambda^\dagger u_R. \quad (5)$$

Here, Λ is a two-by-two matrix. It is not necessarily diagonal, but we have the freedom to perform spinor transformations in the R and L sub-spaces later. It cannot be assumed a priori that Λ is a real field, but the saddle point can be chosen as a real field and can even be constant, like a mass term.

The matrix Λ can equivalently be represented as a four-component field. The latter is achieved by rearranging the two-spinors u_R and u_L into their tensor product, such that

$$\Lambda = \begin{pmatrix} \Lambda_{11} & \Lambda_{12} \\ \Lambda_{21} & \Lambda_{22} \end{pmatrix} \longleftrightarrow \tilde{\Lambda} = \begin{pmatrix} \Lambda_{11} \\ \Lambda_{12} \\ \Lambda_{21} \\ \Lambda_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

with

$$u_R^\dagger \Lambda u_L = -\text{tr} \Lambda u_L u_R^\dagger = - (u_R \otimes u_L^*)^\dagger \tilde{\Lambda} \quad (7)$$

and

$$u_L^\dagger \Lambda^\dagger u_R = -\text{tr} \Lambda^\dagger u_R u_L^\dagger = -\tilde{\Lambda}^\dagger (u_R \otimes u_L^*). \quad (8)$$

Different symbols should be used to distinguish between the matrix and vector representations of Λ , but it might be implied later on. The corresponding compound fields Q can be inserted into the theory by the constraint

$$\delta [Q - u_R u_L^\dagger] \quad \text{or} \quad \delta [\tilde{Q} - u_R \otimes u_L^*] . \quad (9)$$

and the corresponding conjugate expression.¹ Note that if we label the momentum of u_R with p and the momentum of u_L with k , then

$$Q(p, k) \sim u_R(p) u_L^\dagger(k) . \quad (10)$$

In the equal time formulation (i.e., without 'relative time' [1])

$$Q(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}, t) \sim u_R(\mathbf{p}, t) u_L^\dagger(\mathbf{k}, t) . \quad (11)$$

The functional delta functions can be identically re-written as a path integral of $\exp(i\Lambda(Q - u_R u_L^\dagger))$ over a field Λ . By the definition of Q , Λ has the properties described above.

For the interaction between the Weyl fermions let us at this point just assume that a coupling between u_R and u_L exists, such that we can write the potential term symbolically as $-\text{Tr} Q^\dagger V Q$.

¹Regarding the conjugate field Q^\dagger for charged and uncharged fields, see the discussion in [1]. The composite field is only charge neutral in the asymptotic limit. Locally, there can be charged areas, so the field cannot be real valued everywhere.

This formal notation shall include forms like $-\text{Tr}W_1Q^\dagger W_2Q$. E.g., in the special case of Abelian gauge interactions, when integrating out the free fields, the interaction will typically assume a form²

$$u_L^\dagger \tilde{\sigma}^\mu u_L D_{\mu\nu} u_R^\dagger \sigma^\nu u_R \rightarrow -D_{\mu\nu} \text{Tr}\{\tilde{\sigma}^\mu Q^\dagger \sigma^\nu Q\}, \quad (13)$$

where $\sigma = (\mathbb{1}, \boldsymbol{\sigma})^\text{T}$ and $\tilde{\sigma} = (\mathbb{1}, -\boldsymbol{\sigma})^\text{T}$.³ I will show below how such an interaction term can be brought into the form $Q^\dagger V Q$ in an appropriate basis, but for now it is a symbolic notation to represent a Gaussian action in the Q and Q^\dagger fields. The character of the bound state strongly depends on the interaction term and a large variety of interactions can be considered.

3 General effective action

Integrating out the fermion fields u_R and u_L yields the action [1]

$$S_{\text{eff}} = -\text{Tr}Q^\dagger V Q + \text{Tr}\{\Lambda^\dagger Q + Q^\dagger \Lambda\} - i\text{Tr} \ln\{\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda^\dagger G_R \Lambda\} \quad (14)$$

with the Green functions defined as the inverse of the operators

$$G_R^{-1} = i\partial_t - \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \boldsymbol{p}, \quad G_L^{-1} = i\partial_t + \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \boldsymbol{k}. \quad (15)$$

As described in [1], the action can be expanded around a saddle point. The saddle point equation is

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda &= V Q, \\ Q &= -i\text{Tr}' \left\{ \frac{\mathbb{1}}{\mathbb{1} - G_R \Lambda G_L \Lambda^\dagger} G_R \Lambda G_L \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

The symbol Tr' represents the 'open' trace, which integrates out everything except the variables of the function Q occurring on the left hand side. As mentioned before, the symbolical interaction term shall include forms like $-\text{Tr}W_1Q^\dagger W_2Q$, in which case the first equation reads $\Lambda = W_2 Q W_1$ (if W_1 is c-number valued, otherwise the sign changes). Note that in lowest non-trivial order of Λ (i.e. without the Λ terms in the denominator) this is the Bethe-Salpeter equation [1, 2, 7]. The emergence of the denominator in the functional integral approach [1] is crucial for the condensed state.

4 Formal series expansion around the saddle point

Having derived the saddle point equation, the next step is an expansion around the saddle point, i.e., $Q = Q_{\text{SP}} + q$, $\Lambda = \Lambda_{\text{SP}} + \lambda$ etc. For non-commuting objects like matrices and operators, the general expression for the expansion of the logarithmic term around X_0 is

$$\begin{aligned} -\text{tr} \ln [1 - (X_0 + \xi)] &= -\text{tr} \ln [1 - X_0] + \text{tr} \left\{ [1 - X_0]^{-1} \xi \right\} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left\{ [1 - X_0]^{-1} \xi [1 - X_0]^{-1} \xi \right\} + \mathcal{O}(\xi^3) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

²For Grassmann variables the cyclic rotation under the trace obeys

$$\text{tr} \psi_1 \psi_2 \dots \psi_n = (-1)^{n-1} \text{tr} \psi_2 \dots \psi_n \psi_1. \quad (12)$$

³I have taken this notation from [5], but use a different sign convention here.

with

$$\begin{aligned}
X_0 &= G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger, \\
\xi &= \begin{cases} G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_L \lambda^\dagger & \text{from applying } \delta/\delta\Lambda^\dagger, \\ G_R \lambda G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger & \text{from applying } \delta/\delta\Lambda, \\ G_R \lambda G_L \lambda^\dagger & \text{from applying both.} \end{cases} \quad (18)
\end{aligned}$$

The term quadratic in ξ only contains terms quadratic in λ or higher order. The linear term contributes both a linear and a quadratic term. The expansion of the action reads (writing $\text{Tr} W_1 Q^\dagger W_2 Q$ instead of $\text{Tr} Q^\dagger V Q$)

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{\text{eff}} &= S_0 + S_1 + S_2 + \dots, \\
S_0 &= -\text{Tr} W_1 Q_{\text{SP}}^\dagger W_2 Q_{\text{SP}} + \text{Tr} \{ \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger Q_{\text{SP}} + Q_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \} \\
&\quad - i \text{Tr} \ln \{ \mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \}, \\
S_1 &= -\text{Tr} W_1 q^\dagger W_2 Q_{\text{SP}} - \text{Tr} W_1 Q_{\text{SP}}^\dagger W_2 q + \text{Tr} \{ \lambda^\dagger Q_{\text{SP}} + q^\dagger \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \} \\
&\quad + \text{Tr} \{ \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger q + Q_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \lambda \} + i \text{Tr} \left\{ \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \lambda \right\} \\
&\quad + i \text{Tr} \left\{ \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \lambda^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right\}, \\
S_2 &= -\text{Tr} A q^\dagger B q + \text{Tr} \{ \lambda^\dagger q + q^\dagger \lambda \} \\
&\quad + i \text{Tr} \left\{ \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \lambda^\dagger G_R \lambda \right\} \\
&\quad + \frac{i}{2} \text{Tr} \left\{ \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \lambda^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \lambda^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right\} \\
&\quad + \frac{i}{2} \text{Tr} \left\{ \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \lambda^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \lambda \right\} \\
&\quad + \frac{i}{2} \text{Tr} \left\{ \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \lambda \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \lambda^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right\} \\
&\quad + \frac{i}{2} \text{Tr} \left\{ \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \lambda \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \lambda \right\}. \quad (19)
\end{aligned}$$

Note the factors of one-half in front of the last four terms, but also note that amongst them there are two terms with λ and λ^\dagger . These terms can be combined with the term from the linear log expansion terms containing λ and λ^\dagger . To combine them, write

$$\begin{aligned}
&G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \\
&= G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \left[\mathbb{1} - G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \right]^{-1} \\
&= \left(\mathbb{1} - \left[\mathbb{1} - G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \right] \right) \left[\mathbb{1} - G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \right]^{-1} \\
&= \left[\mathbb{1} - G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \right]^{-1} - \mathbb{1}. \quad (20)
\end{aligned}$$

The $\mathbb{1}$ cancels the term from the linear expansion and the full second order term with λ and λ^\dagger becomes

$$i\text{Tr} \left\{ \left[\mathbb{1} - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \right]^{-1} G_L \lambda^\dagger \left[\mathbb{1} - G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \right]^{-1} G_R \lambda \right\} \quad (21)$$

as stated in [1]. However, here the original form is more convenient as will become clear shortly.

5 Change of basis

The above action is a matrix field theory. Since the matrix elements of the action do not commute it is hard to perform actual calculations. In a Gaussian approximation the use of tensor products helps to group all Green functions together. Then it is clear how to perform path integrals. However, this approach is cumbersome for higher order expansions of the field theory.

There is a more convenient basis for such calculations. The massless Weyl fermions come with two helicities. These correspond to two dispersion branches with a crossing point at zero energies. We can switch from that 'helicity' representation to an 'energy' basis, where the two branches of the dispersion are positive and negative energies. These branches do not cross, but touch. Once the interaction between particles is included, the touch points will retreat from each other, forming a gap. But before that happens, the expression of the bare theory in terms of their energy is helpful for calculations.

For the new basis, I use the eigenvectors of $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p}$

$$\varphi_{\mathbf{p},+} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2p(p+p_3)}} \begin{pmatrix} p+p_3 \\ p_1+ip_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_+ = +p, \quad (22)$$

$$\varphi_{\mathbf{p},-} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2p(p+p_3)}} \begin{pmatrix} -p_1+ip_2 \\ p+p_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_- = -p, \quad (23)$$

with $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p} \varphi_{\mathbf{p},s} = sp \varphi_{\mathbf{p},s}$ and $p = |\mathbf{p}|$. These eigenvectors project out components of the Green functions

$$G_{\text{R}}(\mathbf{p}, \omega) = \frac{1}{\omega - \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p}}, \quad G_{\text{L}}(\mathbf{k}, \omega) = \frac{1}{\omega + \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{k}} \quad (24)$$

as

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{\mathbf{p},s}^\dagger G_{\text{R}}(\mathbf{p}, \omega) \varphi_{\mathbf{p},s'} &= G_{\text{R},s}(\mathbf{p}, \omega) \delta_{ss'}, \\ \varphi_{\mathbf{k},s}^\dagger G_{\text{L}}(\mathbf{k}, \omega) \varphi_{\mathbf{k},s'} &= G_{\text{L},s}(\mathbf{k}, \omega) \delta_{ss'} \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{R},s} &= \frac{1}{\omega - sp}, \quad p = |\mathbf{p}|, \\ G_{\text{L},s} &= \frac{1}{\omega + sk}, \quad k = |\mathbf{k}|. \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

This means that for right-handed particles $s = +$ represents positive eigenenergies, etc. We define

$$\Lambda_{ss'} := \varphi_{\mathbf{p},s}^\dagger \Lambda(\omega, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}) \varphi_{\mathbf{k},s'} \quad (27)$$

and

$$\Lambda_{s's}^\dagger(k, p) := \varphi_{\mathbf{k},s'}^\dagger (\Lambda((\omega, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}))^\dagger \varphi_{\mathbf{p},s}, \quad s, s' = +, - . \quad (28)$$

Including the sums over s and s' into the trace, the lowest order quadratic term reads

$$i\text{Tr}\{G_L\Lambda^\dagger G_R\Lambda\} = i\text{Tr}\{G_{L,s'}\Lambda_{s's}^\dagger G_{R,s}\Lambda_{ss'}\} = \text{Tr}\{\Lambda_{s's}^\dagger (iG_{L,s'}G_{R,s}) \Lambda_{ss'}\} , \quad (29)$$

where in the last step the Green's function could be moved around freely. In order to see why this is a big improvement, let us define

$$\bar{\Lambda} = \begin{pmatrix} \Lambda_{++} & \Lambda_{+-} \\ \Lambda_{-+} & \Lambda_{--} \end{pmatrix} , \quad \bar{Q} = \begin{pmatrix} Q_{++} & Q_{+-} \\ Q_{-+} & Q_{--} \end{pmatrix} \quad (30)$$

and

$$\bar{G}_R = \begin{pmatrix} G_{R,+} & 0 \\ 0 & G_{R,-} \end{pmatrix} , \quad \bar{G}_L = \begin{pmatrix} G_{L,+} & 0 \\ 0 & G_{L,-} \end{pmatrix} \quad (31)$$

and write the action as

$$S_{\text{eff}} = -\text{Tr}\bar{Q}^\dagger\bar{V}\bar{Q} + \text{Tr}\{\bar{\Lambda}^\dagger\bar{Q} + \bar{Q}^\dagger\bar{\Lambda}\} - i\text{Tr}\ln\{\mathbb{1} - \bar{G}_L\bar{\Lambda}^\dagger\bar{G}_R\bar{\Lambda}\} . \quad (32)$$

Note, again, that \bar{V} symbolizes the interaction, which for (gauge) interactions between Weyl fermions be will be of the form $\text{Tr}\bar{W}_1\bar{Q}^\dagger\bar{W}_2\bar{Q}$. Further, for the terms arising in the saddle point equation, define auxiliary matrix elements A trough D via

$$\bar{G}_R\bar{\Lambda}\bar{G}_L\bar{\Lambda}^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} \quad (33)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} A &= G_{R,+}\Lambda_{++}G_{R,+}\Lambda_{++} + G_{R,+}\Lambda_{+-}G_{L,-}\Lambda_{+-}^* , \\ B &= G_{R,+}\Lambda_{++}G_{L,+}\Lambda_{-+}^* + G_{R,+}\Lambda_{+-}G_{R,-}\Lambda_{--} , \\ C &= G_{R,-}\Lambda_{-+}G_{R,+}\Lambda_{++} + G_{R,-}\Lambda_{--}G_{L,-}\Lambda_{+-}^* , \\ D &= G_{R,-}\Lambda_{-+}G_{L,+}\Lambda_{-+}^* + G_{R,-}\Lambda_{--}G_{R,-}\Lambda_{--} . \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

The denominator in the saddle point equation then reads

$$\left[1 - \bar{G}_R\bar{\Lambda}\bar{G}_L\bar{\Lambda}^\dagger\right]^{-1} = \frac{1}{(1-A)(1-D) - CB} \begin{pmatrix} 1-D & B \\ C & 1-A \end{pmatrix} . \quad (35)$$

For integrations related to the expansion around the saddle point, the poles, i.e., the zeros of the denominator $(1-A)(1-D) - CB$, are relevant. Here, I will not go into details of the general case, but consider special cases only.

Simple special cases are those, where $\bar{G}_R\bar{\Lambda}\bar{G}_L\bar{\Lambda}^\dagger$ is diagonal. This is the case (e.g.) if only fields with the same energy index occur (only Λ_{++} and Λ_{--} with their conjugates) or if only fields with opposite energy index occur (only Λ_{+-} and Λ_{-+} with their conjugates). Then

$$\left[1 - \bar{G}_R\bar{\Lambda}\bar{G}_L\bar{\Lambda}^\dagger\right]^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{1-A} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{1-D} \end{pmatrix} \quad (36)$$

and the poles are A and B . But then, as we will see below, the energy integral over the internal lines will only let survive the case where the energy index is the same (only Λ_{++} and Λ_{--} with their conjugates).

Let's consider the effect of the basis change for a Coulomb-like interaction term like assumed above,

$$-D_{\mu\nu}\text{Tr}\{\tilde{\sigma}^\mu Q^\dagger \sigma^\nu Q\} = -D_{\mu\nu}\text{Tr}\{\tilde{\sigma}_{s'r'}^\mu (Q^\dagger)_{r',r} \sigma_{r,s}^\nu Q_{ss'}\} \quad (37)$$

and since all the terms can be moved around freely now, this part of the action now reads

$$-\text{Tr}\left\{\left(Q^\dagger\right)_{r',r} V_{rr',ss'} Q_{ss'}\right\} \quad (38)$$

with

$$V_{rr',ss'} = \tilde{\sigma}_{s'r'}^\mu D_{\mu\nu} \sigma_{r,s}^\nu . \quad (39)$$

This justifies the formal notation $-\text{Tr}\{Q^\dagger V Q\}$ used earlier.

6 The saddle point equation

In the new basis the saddle point equation reads

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{Q} &= -i \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \left\{ \frac{\mathbb{1}}{\mathbb{1} - \bar{G}_R \bar{\Lambda} \bar{G}_L \bar{\Lambda}^\dagger} \bar{G}_R \bar{\Lambda} \bar{G}_L \right\} , \\ \bar{\Lambda} &= \bar{V} \bar{Q} , \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

where \bar{V} is the interaction projected to the new basis (and can look like Eq. (39)).

To proceed we consider the case where the fields in the new basis are diagonal or completely off-diagonal. Already the more restrictive case where all is diagonal is not just an arbitrary assumption. If we start from a free theory and then turn on an interaction, both the Λ fields and the Green function will transform together. But if the interaction is not too large, it will not mix negative and positive energy solutions. The positive and negative energy solutions, for which the dispersion curves only touched at one point, have separated and the positive and negative energy solutions will still not mix if the excitations are small enough. Only at some high enough energies they will start mixing.

Within this approximation the expression simplifies to

$$\bar{Q} = -i \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{G_{R,+} G_{L,+}}{1 - G_{R,+} G_{L,+} |\Lambda_{++}|^2} \Lambda_{++} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{G_{R,-} G_{L,-}}{1 - G_{R,-} G_{L,-} |\Lambda_{--}|^2} \Lambda_{--} \end{pmatrix} \quad (41)$$

for the purely diagonal case and

$$\bar{Q} = -i \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{G_{R,+} G_{L,-}}{1 - G_{R,+} G_{L,-} \Lambda_{+-} \Lambda_{-+}^*} \Lambda_{+-} \\ \frac{G_{R,-} G_{L,+}}{1 - G_{R,-} G_{L,+} \Lambda_{-+} \Lambda_{+-}^*} \Lambda_{-+} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (42)$$

for the purely non-diagonal case. All the integrals over internal energies to solve can be summarized as

$$Q_{ss'} = -i \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \frac{G_{R,s} G_{L,s'}}{1 - G_{R,s} G_{L,s'} \Lambda_{ss'} \Lambda_{s's}^*} \Lambda_{ss'} . \quad (43)$$

In the equal time approach chosen here, Λ does not depend on ϵ , so

$$Q_{ss'} = -\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)} \Lambda_{ss'} \quad (44)$$

with

$$\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)} = i \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \frac{1}{G_{R,s}^{-1} G_{L,s'}^{-1} - \Lambda_{ss'} \Lambda_{s's}^*} \Lambda_{ss'} . \quad (45)$$

For the calculation of the integral, please see appendix 9.1. The result is

$$\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)}(\omega, \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p}) = -\frac{s\delta_{ss'} \text{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))}{\sqrt{(\omega - s(p+k))^2 + 4|\Lambda_{ss'}|^2 + is\eta \text{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))}} , \quad (46)$$

where $p = |\mathbf{p}|$ (right-handed particles) and $k = |\mathbf{k}|$ (left-handed particles) and η is an infinitesimal pole shift.⁴ The integral for $s \neq s'$ vanishes both for the trivial saddle point, where $|\Lambda_{ss}| = 0$ everywhere, and the non-trivial saddle point, where $|\Lambda_{ss}| \neq 0$. Remember, however, that this holds only for the subset of solutions considered above. Under these circumstances, \bar{Q} is diagonal.

The interaction for diagonal \bar{Q} and $\bar{\Lambda}$ simplifies, as well. Before we set all indices to zero, we remark that for equal s indices, the matrix elements $\tilde{\sigma}_{s,s}^\nu$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{s's'}^0 &= \tilde{\sigma}_{ss}^0 = \mathbb{1} \\ \sigma_{s's'}^i &= \varphi_{\mathbf{p},s'}^\dagger \sigma^i \varphi_{\mathbf{p},s'} = s' \frac{p_i}{p} \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{ss}^j &= -\varphi_{\mathbf{k},s}^\dagger \sigma^j \varphi_{\mathbf{k},s} = -s \frac{k_j}{k} \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

while the expressions for $s \neq s'$ are more cumbersome. With this, the interaction term reads

$$-\text{Tr} \left\{ \left(Q^\dagger \right)_{s',s} V_{ss',ss'} Q_{ss'} \right\} , \quad V_{ss',ss'} = D_{00} + s D_{i0} \frac{p_i}{p} - s' \frac{k_j}{k} D_{0j} \text{Tr} - s s' \frac{p_i}{p} D_{ij} \frac{k_j}{k} . \quad (48)$$

Despite the gauge constraint $q^\mu D_{\mu\nu} = 0$ and $D_{\mu\nu} q^\nu = 0$ in all Lorentz gauges, we have to keep in mind that p^μ and k^μ cannot be assumed to point along q^μ .

As a special case consider a decomposition into a static part and a dynamic part

$$D_{\mu\nu}(\mathbf{q}, \omega) = D_{\mu\nu}^0(\mathbf{q}, 0) + D_{\mu\nu}^{\text{dyn}}(\mathbf{q}, \omega) . \quad (49)$$

This is the case when working in the Coulomb gauge (for an Abelian gauge theory or the Gaussian approximation of a non-Abelian gauge theory, neglecting self-interactions) and in the non-retarded

⁴I assume there is no danger from recycling the notation p and k , earlier used for four-vectors, now re-used as norm of three-vectors.

limit: With $i, j = 1, 2, 3$, this special case reads [7]

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{00}(\mathbf{q}) &= \frac{4\pi}{\mathbf{q}^2} \\
D_{0j}(\mathbf{q}) &= 0 = D_{i0}(\mathbf{q}) \\
D_{ij}(\mathbf{q}) &= \frac{4\pi}{q^2 + i\eta} \left(\delta_{ij} - \frac{q_i q_j}{\mathbf{q}^2} \right) \rightarrow -\frac{4\pi}{\mathbf{q}^2} \left(\delta_{ij} - \frac{q_i q_j}{\mathbf{q}^2} \right), \tag{50}
\end{aligned}$$

such that

$$V_{ss',ss'} = \frac{4\pi g_R g_L}{\mathbf{q}^2} \left[1 + ss' \left(\frac{\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{k}}{pk} - \frac{(\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{q})(\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{k})}{\mathbf{q}^2 pk} \right) \right]. \tag{51}$$

In the center-of-mass frame,

$$V_{ss',ss'} = \frac{4\pi g_R g_L}{\mathbf{q}^2} \left(\mathbb{1} + 4ss' \frac{\mathbf{P}^2 - \frac{(\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{q})^2}{\mathbf{q}^2}}{\sqrt{(\mathbf{P}^2 + \mathbf{q}^2)^2 - 4(\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{q})^2}} \right). \tag{52}$$

The omission of the retardation makes it convenient for the center-of-mass frame. However, for the infinite-momentum frame (light-cone frame) it is not very useful. Note that the expressions derived above are essentially the Breit interaction for two-spinors instead of four-spinors,

$$V_{ss',ss'}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{4\pi g_R g_L}{r} \left\{ \mathbb{1} \cdot \mathbb{1} - ss' \frac{1}{2} \left[\boldsymbol{\sigma} \odot \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \frac{\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{x} \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{x}}{r^2} \right] \right\} \tag{53}$$

with the abbreviation $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \odot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \sum_i \sigma_R^i \otimes \sigma_L^i$.

We now use this result in the system of equations (40). As \bar{Q} is diagonal, we can write the diagonal elements into a two-dimensional vector and express the interaction terms (restricted to $s = s'$ for in-going and out-going pairs) as

$$\underline{Q} = \begin{pmatrix} Q_{++} \\ Q_{--} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \underline{V} = \begin{pmatrix} V_{++,++} & V_{++,--} \\ V_{--,++} & V_{--,--} \end{pmatrix}. \tag{54}$$

I have kept the non-diagonal terms for completeness, despite the fact that I have not treated them in the special case above. The special case is more for illustration and to make it more tangible. We can also invert $\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)}$ and write the inverse as

$$\underline{G}_0^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} G_{0,+}^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & G_{0,-}^{-1} \end{pmatrix} \tag{55}$$

with

$$G_{0,s}^{-1} = s \operatorname{sign}(\omega - s(p+k)) \sqrt{(\omega - s(p+k))^2 + 4|\Lambda_{ss}|^2} \tag{56}$$

or, explicitly,

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{0,+}^{-1} &= \operatorname{sign}(\omega - (p+k)) \sqrt{(\omega - (p+k))^2 + 4|\Lambda_{++}|^2} \\
G_{0,-}^{-1} &= -\operatorname{sign}(\omega + (p+k)) \sqrt{(\omega + (p+k))^2 + 4|\Lambda_{--}|^2} \tag{57}
\end{aligned}$$

The resulting equation is

$$\left[\underline{\underline{G}}_0^{-1} - \underline{\underline{V}} \right] \underline{\underline{Q}} = 0. \quad (58)$$

This is the saddle point equation, which determines the saddle point solution $\underline{\underline{Q}}(\omega, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})$ and at the same time $\underline{\underline{\Lambda}}(\omega, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})$. This equation almost has Schrodinger form, but in the given shape the Green operator does not have the form $i\partial_t - H_0$ due to the square root. We can achieve such a form by observing that for a given s the matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} (\omega - s(p+k)) & \pm 2\Lambda_{ss}^* \\ \pm 2\Lambda_{ss} & -(\omega - s(p+k)) \end{pmatrix} =: \underline{\underline{G}}_{0,s}^{\prime-1} \quad (59)$$

has the eigenvalues

$$\pm \text{sign}(\omega - s(p+k)) \sqrt{(\omega - s(p+k))^2 + 4|\Lambda_{ss}|^2}. \quad (60)$$

The problem is, however, that the eigenvalues come with both signs. We can still use it and expand the dimensions; in the end we have to project to get desired 1 and 4 components:

$$\left[\underline{\underline{G}}_0^{\prime-1} - \underline{\underline{V}}' \right] \underline{\underline{Q}}' = 0, \quad \underline{\underline{Q}} = P_{14} \underline{\underline{Q}}' \quad (61)$$

with

$$\underline{\underline{G}}_0^{\prime-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{\underline{G}}_{0,+}^{\prime-1} & 0 \\ 0 & \underline{\underline{G}}_{0,-}^{\prime-1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (62)$$

Here, the notation $\underline{\underline{Q}}$ has been re-used for the four-dimensional vector with zeros in the added components. The projector is supposed to operate in four-dimensional vector space, such that we can rotate it below when we change basis. The generalization of the potential term is not unique, but the projections are. This is a kind of gauge freedom. One choice would be

$$\underline{\underline{V}}' = \begin{pmatrix} V_{+,+,+}\sigma_3 & V_{+,+,-}\sigma_1 \\ V_{-,-,+}\sigma_1 & -V_{-,-,-}\sigma_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (63)$$

but others are equally possible. We can rotate the basis

$$\underline{\underline{V}}'' = \underline{\underline{U}} \underline{\underline{V}}' \underline{\underline{U}}^\dagger, \quad \underline{\underline{Q}}'' = \underline{\underline{U}} \underline{\underline{Q}}', \quad (64)$$

to obtain

$$\left[\underline{\underline{G}}_0'' - \underline{\underline{V}}'' \right] \underline{\underline{Q}}'' = 0, \quad \underline{\underline{Q}} = P_{14} \underline{\underline{U}}^{-1} \underline{\underline{Q}}'' \quad (65)$$

with the Green operator (choosing the appropriate sign in front of the Λ terms)

$$\underline{\underline{G}}_0'' = \begin{pmatrix} (\omega - (p+k)) & \pm 2\Lambda_{++}^* & 0 & 0 \\ \pm 2\Lambda_{++} & -(\omega - (p+k)) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (\omega + (p+k)) & \pm 2\Lambda_{--}^* \\ 0 & 0 & \pm 2\Lambda_{--} & -(\omega + (p+k)) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (66)$$

The potential term and the projector have also been rotated and have some non-trivial dependence on ω , $p + q$, and the Λ terms. The resulting equation of motion can already be called Schroedinger form. However, it still is non-linear in the momentum operators. It can be linearized by noting that

$$(\sigma_R \otimes \mathbb{1}) \cdot \mathbf{p} + (\mathbb{1} \otimes \sigma_L) \cdot \mathbf{k} \quad (67)$$

has eigenvalues $s(p + k)$. In order to apply this, we first apply a unitary transformation to re-order the components of \underline{H}_0 as follows:⁵

$$\underline{\tilde{G}}''_0 = \begin{pmatrix} (\omega - (p + k)) & 0 & \pm 2\Lambda_{++}^* & 0 \\ 0 & (\omega + (p + k)) & 0 & \pm 2\Lambda_{--}^* \\ \pm 2\Lambda_{++} & 0 & -(\omega - (p + k)) & 0 \\ 0 & \pm 2\Lambda_{--} & 0 & -(\omega + (p + k)) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (69)$$

Note that we can write

$$\underline{\tilde{G}}''_0 = \begin{pmatrix} \omega \mathbb{1} - (p + k)\sigma_3 & 2\Lambda_{\text{mat}}^\dagger \\ 2\Lambda_{\text{mat}} & -\omega \mathbb{1} + (p + k)\sigma_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (70)$$

with a matrix Λ_{mat} for the off-diagonal blocks in the previous expression. Now we can rotate the first two and the last two components separately to get

$$\underline{\tilde{G}}'''_0 = \begin{pmatrix} \omega \mathbb{1} - [(\sigma_R \otimes \mathbb{1}) \cdot \mathbf{p} + (\mathbb{1} \otimes \sigma_L) \cdot \mathbf{k}] & 2\Lambda_{\text{mat}'}^\dagger \\ 2\Lambda_{\text{mat}'} & -\omega \mathbb{1} + [(\sigma_R \otimes \mathbb{1}) \cdot \mathbf{p} + (\mathbb{1} \otimes \sigma_L) \cdot \mathbf{k}] \end{pmatrix}. \quad (71)$$

An interesting special case is $\Lambda_{++} = \Lambda_{--}$, which encourages to define $m := \Lambda = \Lambda^*$ and $M := 2m$. Then Λ_{mat} is proportional to the identity matrix and so $\Lambda_{\text{mat}'}$ also must be proportional to the identity matrix. This is a particularly simple form, but requires the equality of the $++$ and $--$ saddle points.

In order to bring this into Schroedinger form, define

$$\beta = \sigma_3 \otimes \mathbb{1} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{1} & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathbb{1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (72)$$

and write

$$\underline{\tilde{G}}'''_0 = \beta [i\partial_t - H_0'''] \quad (73)$$

with

$$H_0''' = \begin{pmatrix} (\sigma_R \otimes \mathbb{1}) \cdot \mathbf{p} + (\mathbb{1} \otimes \sigma_L) \cdot \mathbf{k} & -2\Lambda_{\text{mat}'}^\dagger \\ +2\Lambda_{\text{mat}'} & (\sigma_R \otimes \mathbb{1}) \cdot \mathbf{p} + (\mathbb{1} \otimes \sigma_L) \cdot \mathbf{k} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (74)$$

⁵An alternative ordering of rows and columns would be

$$\underline{\tilde{G}}'''_0 = \begin{pmatrix} (\omega - (p + k)) & 0 & 0 & \pm 2\Lambda_{++}^* \\ 0 & (\omega + (p + k)) & \pm 2\Lambda_{--}^* & 0 \\ 0 & \pm 2\Lambda_{--} & -(\omega + (p + k)) & 0 \\ \pm 2\Lambda_{++} & 0 & 0 & -(\omega - (p + k)) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (68)$$

The final step is to separate this into center-of-mass momentum and momentum exchange. Then

$$\left\{ \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{1} & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathbb{1} \end{pmatrix} \omega - \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{P} & 0 \\ 0 & -\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{P} \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}' \cdot \mathbf{q} & 2\bar{\Lambda} \\ 2\bar{\Lambda}^\dagger & -\boldsymbol{\Sigma}' \cdot \mathbf{q} \end{pmatrix} - \mathcal{V} \right\} \bar{Q} = 0 \quad (75)$$

where \mathcal{V} is obtained by pulling out β from the V'' matrix,

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\Sigma} &= \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_R \otimes \mathbb{1}_L + \mathbb{1}_R \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma}_L) , \\ \boldsymbol{\Sigma}' &= \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_R \otimes \mathbb{1}_L - \mathbb{1}_R \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma}_L) , \end{aligned} \quad (76)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P} &= \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{k} , \\ \mathbf{q} &= \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k} \equiv 2\mathbf{p}_{\text{rel}} . \end{aligned} \quad (77)$$

From this equation, eigen-solutions can be derived. From the relative motion follow eigen-solutions for the localized bound state. If the potential (and mass term) allow it, it has a defined 'Bohr' radius. These eigen-solutions can be normalized and then be used to obtain an equation for the remaining center-of-mass motion. Note that the complete solutions are not normalized wave-functions and the size of the center-of-mass part of Λ itself has to be derived from a self-consistency equation. For example, we can follow the example of BCS theory and determine it by self-consistency like (e.g.)

$$\bar{\Lambda} = -i\langle \mathcal{V} \rangle \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \frac{\bar{\Lambda}}{G_{R,+}^{-1}(\epsilon, \mathbf{k}) G_{L,+}^{-1}(\epsilon, \mathbf{k}) - |\bar{\Lambda}|^2} \quad (78)$$

for the zero Fourier component ($\omega = 0$ and $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}$). The average $\langle \mathcal{V} \rangle$ is the quantum mechanical expectation value of the potential in the given eigenstate of the relative motion. For every eigen-energy there is such a self-consistency equation, but in a condensate we will usually consider the ground state of the relative motion and expect that the resulting average Λ_0 is the correct prefactor for all the eigen-solutions.⁶ Put differently, we determine a single parameter (matrix) $\bar{\Lambda}_0$ from the ground state and use it as fixed parameter in Eq. (75).

Without a cut-off for high momenta the integral as written here is highly divergent. However, note that the integral has a physical cutoff at the 'Bohr' radius. At momenta comparable to the inverse 'Bohr' radius, the bound states would dissolve and the component particle theory takes over. Further, the equations should contain both the negative and the positive energy components. If they are equal, the integrals get further regularized.

The $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ matrices in the saddle point equation obey the algebra

$$\begin{aligned} [\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_j] &= i\epsilon_{ijk} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_k , \\ [\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}'_j] &= i\epsilon_{ijk} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}'_k , \\ [\boldsymbol{\Sigma}'_i, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}'_j] &= i\epsilon_{ijk} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_k , \end{aligned} \quad (79)$$

which is equivalent to the algebra of the Lorentz group. Firstly, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ forms a closed sub-algebra corresponding to an angular momentum (rotations). Secondly, $i\boldsymbol{\Sigma}'$ corresponds to a momentum

⁶Note that Λ is actually expanded in eigenstates for the relative motion and the coefficients are fields of the center-of-mass motion. The zero center-of-mass coefficient is called Λ_0 here.

(Lorentz boosts). Not surprisingly, this is spin one and Σ contains the generators of SO(3). The commutator of the total spin operator

$$\mathbf{S} = \frac{\hbar}{2}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_R + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_L) \equiv \Sigma \quad (80)$$

with the Hamiltonian is

$$[\mathbf{S}, H] = i\hbar(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_R \times \mathbf{p}_R + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_L \times \mathbf{p}_L) \neq 0 \quad (81)$$

which is expected, because we need to consider orbital angular momentum as well. With

$$\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{x}_R \times \mathbf{p}_R + \mathbf{x}_L \times \mathbf{p}_L \quad (82)$$

we find

$$[\mathbf{L}, H] = -i\hbar(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_R \times \mathbf{p}_R + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_L \times \mathbf{p}_L) \neq 0 \quad (83)$$

and so for the total angular momentum

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J} &= \mathbf{L} + \mathbf{S}, \\ [\mathbf{J}, H] &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

We can transform into a singlet-triplet representation using

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (85)$$

Then

$$UHU^\dagger = \tilde{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{P} + \tilde{\Sigma}' \cdot \mathbf{p} \quad (86)$$

with

$$\tilde{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{P} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathcal{P} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \tilde{\Sigma}' \cdot \mathbf{p} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \tilde{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \\ \tilde{\mathbf{p}} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (87)$$

where

$$\mathcal{P} = \begin{pmatrix} P_3 & P_- & 0 \\ P_+ & 0 & P_- \\ 0 & P_+ & -P_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad P_\pm = \frac{P_1 \pm iP_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad (88)$$

and

$$\tilde{\mathbf{p}} = \begin{pmatrix} -p_- \\ p_3 \\ p_+ \end{pmatrix}, \quad p_\pm = \frac{p_1 \pm ip_2}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (89)$$

Note that the definition of p_{\pm} contains an extra factor of $1/\sqrt{2}$ and so

$$p^2 = |\mathbf{p}|^2 = 2p_+p_- + p_3^2. \quad (90)$$

The matrix \mathcal{P} , which is Hermitian, can be diagonalized, which is most easily achieved by pointing the CM momentum in axis in 3-direction. Then

$$\mathcal{P}_{\text{diagonal}} = \begin{pmatrix} P & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -P \end{pmatrix} \quad (91)$$

and so

$$\left(\tilde{\Sigma} \cdot \mathcal{P}\right)_{\text{diagonal}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & P & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -P \end{pmatrix}. \quad (92)$$

Again, it looks like the spin-mixed states have to drop out to give a consistent theory. Technically, the path integral over the spin 0 components for which the Gaussian term is zero yields a 'delta functional'. This pins the Q field components to zero, such that the remaining theory only contains spin +1 and spin -1.

So, as expected, the massless case only contains maximum spin, i.e., spin +1 and spin -1, but not spin 0. This is analog to the case of massless gauge bosons, but as we shall see, there are differences. If we add masses (for a non-zero saddle point) the spin 0 components play a role.

The general equations might look uninviting, but in order to get a quick insight (at least for the trivial saddle point) the infinite momentum frame might help. The following lines should come with a warning, as the binding potential part heavily depends on assumptions on the interaction. So the special case considered might be completely unphysical, but interesting enough to understand some important features. Firstly, following the standard procedure,

$$p + k \approx P \left(1 + \frac{q^2}{2P^2} \left[1 - \frac{(\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{q})^2}{q^2 P^2} \right] \right) = P \left(1 + \frac{q^2 \sin^2 \theta}{2P^2} \right). \quad (93)$$

If we choose the z -axis in the direction of \mathbf{P} , then

$$p + k \approx P \left(1 + \frac{q_x^2 + q_y^2}{2P^2} \right). \quad (94)$$

This is P plus a classical two-dimensional Hamiltonian

$$p + k \approx P + \frac{q_x^2 + q_y^2}{2m}, \text{ mass } m = P \quad (95)$$

where the mass m is just an analogy mass. Unfortunately, the non-retarded limit of the Coulomb gauge is not ideal for this limit. The light-cone gauge expression is not straightforward, so I will not expand on it. Instead I rely on dimensional arguments.

Let's take a look at the vicinity of the trivial saddle point for simplicity. Formally, we can consider the 'Schroedinger equation'

$$[\omega - (p + k) + V] \psi = 0 \rightarrow \left[i\partial_t - cP - \frac{q_x^2 + q_y^2}{2m} + V \right] \psi = 0, \quad (96)$$

recovering the speed of light c , i.e., the mass is now $m = cP$. The equation for the relative motion is a non-relativistic Schroedinger equation

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar}{2m}\Delta + V \right] \psi = E\psi . \quad (97)$$

Despite the reduction to two dimensions, let's assume that the physical dimension of the potential is still 1/length, like a Coulomb potential in three dimensions. A hand-waving reasoning could go as follows. The Laplacian, even if two-dimensional, has dimension 1/length². Despite the fact that we do not have a three-dimensional Coulomb problem in this frame and despite the fact that the rotational symmetry is broken, due to dimensional reasons the Bohr radius must still be proportional to \hbar^2/mg^2 (g is the coupling constant) and the eigen-energies must still be proportional to mg^4/\hbar^2 . The prefactors must differ from the hydrogen problem, but for dimensional reasons and the lack of any additional length parameter the physical scale must be determined by the same energy scale. The energy scale is proportional to m and so it is proportional to cP . If the 'wave function' ψ is expanded in the eigenstates of the relative motion, $\psi = \sum_n \phi_{\text{rel},n} \chi_{\text{cm},n}$, then the center-of-mass motion obeys

$$[i\partial_t - cP - cP\epsilon_n] \chi_{\text{cm},n} = 0 , \quad (98)$$

with dimensionless $\epsilon_n < 0$. This means

$$[i\partial_t - c'P] \chi_{\text{cm},n} = 0 , \quad (99)$$

with a renormalized speed

$$c' = c(1 - |\epsilon_n|) < c . \quad (100)$$

The effect of spontaneous coupling without forming a massive state is that the particle is slowed down. The naive picture is that the particles spiral around each other, both moving at the speed of light, but not on a straight path. However, this interpretation might look somewhat problematic, because it would mean that the helicity cannot be preserved while the equations seem to preserve it. A way to resolve this contradiction is to interpret this property as a kind of forward scattering. Once in a while, the helicity flips, but has to flip back on a very short time scale. The helicity is indeed not strictly conserved, which is a sort of precursor of a massive state. Remember that this example depends highly on assumption on the binding potential.

7 The Gaussian action

In the new basis the second order action term and in the approximation in which the fields are diagonal, the action becomes simpler. I will suppress the energy indices for easier notation.

$$\begin{aligned}
S_2 &= -\text{Tr}q^\dagger Vq + \text{Tr}\{\lambda^\dagger q + q^\dagger \lambda\} \\
&+ i\text{Tr}\left\{\lambda^\dagger \frac{G_L G_R}{1 - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}}}\lambda\right\} \\
&+ \frac{i}{2}\text{Tr}\left\{\lambda^\dagger \frac{(G_L G_R)^2}{(1 - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}})^2} \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \lambda^\dagger\right\} \\
&+ \frac{i}{2}\text{Tr}\left\{\lambda^\dagger \frac{(G_L G_R)^2}{(1 - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}})^2} \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \lambda\right\} \\
&+ \frac{i}{2}\text{Tr}\left\{\lambda \frac{(G_L G_R)^2}{(1 - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}})^2} \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \lambda^\dagger\right\} \\
&+ \frac{i}{2}\text{Tr}\left\{\lambda \frac{(G_L G_R)^2}{(1 - G_L \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_R \Lambda_{\text{SP}})^2} \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \lambda\right\}. \tag{101}
\end{aligned}$$

A compact notation for this is

$$\begin{aligned}
S_2 &= -\text{Tr}q^\dagger Vq + \text{Tr}\{\lambda^\dagger q + q^\dagger \lambda\} \\
&+ i\text{Tr}\left\{\lambda^\dagger \mathcal{G} \lambda\right\}, \tag{102}
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\lambda = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda \\ \lambda^\dagger \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda^\dagger = (\lambda^\dagger, \lambda) \tag{103}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{G} &= \mathcal{G}_1 \mathbb{1} + \mathcal{G}_2 \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \\
\mathcal{G}_1 &= i \int \frac{1}{G_L^{-1} G_R^{-1} - |\Lambda_{\text{SP}}|^2} \\
\mathcal{G}_2 &= \frac{i}{2} \int \frac{1}{(G_L^{-1} G_R^{-1} - |\Lambda_{\text{SP}}|^2)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial (|\Lambda_{\text{SP}}|^2)} \mathcal{G}_1 \\
\Lambda_{\text{SP}} &= \begin{pmatrix} \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \\ \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger = (\Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger, \Lambda_{\text{SP}}). \tag{104}
\end{aligned}$$

The notation \int shall refer to all summations and integrals over internal degrees of freedom. Remember that all expression come with energy indices ss' (with $s = s'$ in the approximation used),

i.e., everything comes with positive and negative energies. Keeping the two momenta and only integrating out the frequency, a calculation yields (see appendices)

$$\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)}(\omega, \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p}) = -\frac{s\delta_{ss'}\text{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))}{\sqrt{(\omega - s(p+k))^2 + 4|\Lambda_{ss'}|^2 + is\eta \text{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))}} \quad (105)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(2)}(\omega, \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p}) &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)}(\omega, \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p})}{(\omega - s(p+k))^2 + 4|\Lambda_{ss'}|^2 + is\eta \text{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{s\delta_{ss'}\text{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))}{[(\omega - s(p+k))^2 + 4|\Lambda_{ss'}|^2]^{3/2} + is\eta \text{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))}. \end{aligned} \quad (106)$$

Indeed, \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 come with different signs.

The eigenvectors of \mathcal{G} in this new two-dimensional space are easy to find:

$$\mathbf{v}_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2|\Lambda_{\text{SP}}|^2}} \begin{pmatrix} \Lambda_{\text{SP}} \\ \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{v}_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2|\Lambda_{\text{SP}}|^2}} \begin{pmatrix} \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger \\ -\Lambda_{\text{SP}} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (107)$$

The eigenvalues of \mathcal{G} are

$$\chi_1 = \mathcal{G}_1 + 2|\Lambda_{\text{SP}}|^2\mathcal{G}_2, \quad \chi_2 = \mathcal{G}_1, \quad (108)$$

but for the effective Gaussian action the potential part needs to be included. To that end, let's formally integrate out q and q^\dagger and treat the interaction potential as invertible, adding to \mathcal{G}_1 . Then

$$\chi'_1 = \mathcal{G}_1 + V^{-1} + 2|\Lambda_{\text{SP}}|^2\mathcal{G}_2, \quad \chi'_2 = \mathcal{G}_1 + V^{-1}. \quad (109)$$

The sum $\mathcal{G}_1 + V^{-1}$ represents the operator, which lets the field vanish at the saddle point. So we set it to zero, while the part containing \mathcal{G}_2 survives. What remains, if the common part vanishes, is

$$\chi'_1 = 2|\Lambda_{\text{SP}}|^2\mathcal{G}_2, \quad \chi'_2 = 0. \quad (110)$$

It should be noted that this is a zero temperature calculation. At finite temperatures (even if small) a too small energy gain from the potential will not suffice to enable a non-trivial saddle point. In particular, when crossing through a larger temperature range, non-trivial saddle points will be found when cooling below certain temperatures, depending on the strength of the attractive interaction.

The Gaussian approximation has brought up a two-component field $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$, where the components are a massless boson and a massive boson. The mass of the massive boson is the zero frequency and zero relative momentum limit of $2|\Lambda_{\text{SP}}|^2\mathcal{G}_2$. So we find that the fields describing bound pairs of Weyl fermions can end in a Mexican hat potential. If an appropriate vector potential is coupled to the resulting boson or results from the constituent couplings, then the Anderson-Higgs mechanism⁷ might apply and remove the mass-less modes.

It is interesting to note that the saddle point can be transformed by any operation which leaves $|\Lambda|^2$ unchanged. But in addition to this symmetry structure, we see from the eigenvectors that excitations with the same charge configuration as the saddle point (along \mathbf{v}_1) are massive, while

⁷See, e.g., [8] for the Higgs mechanism.

those that deviate from that configuration (along \mathbf{v}_2) are massless. So, if the saddle point is chosen strictly real, then the fluctuations around it correspond to a massive real field excitation and a massless complex field. This corresponds to an uncharged massive component and a charged massless component of the bound state bosonic field configuration. Note that the multiple components emerge from the fermion structure and are not necessarily forced on the system by a gauge field structure.

Thus, for removing the massless modes, a coupling to a gauge field would be required. An interesting application would be a composite Higgs (toy) model.⁸ The above shows that the technical requirements are given. There are some objections to an application to the physical Higgs. E.g., it seems that each particle would need its own Higgs, which contradicts observation. On the other hand, this objection is not fully applicable. Firstly, if there are towers of eigenstates they all share the same potential and scale by the same interaction strength. Secondly, it is possible to have a condensate, where many different constituents coexist, i.e., there is not even a restriction to one tower of eigenstates.

One other difference is that the free composite boson, as obtained here, fulfills a first order differential equation, unlike in the actual acknowledged model, for which the free part obeys a Klein-Gordon equation. The potential coefficients for the spin-0 boson in the standard theory are free parameters, while in the theory here they are interlocked.

A short remark on the massless modes might be in place. In the case with condensation, we can hope for the Anderson-Higgs mechanism to remove them. However, it seems that there is no general argument that all massless modes always disappear. If there are Weyl fermions and they have an attractive interaction, what happens to spontaneously built bound states? E.g., consider massless fermions propagating through space and once in a while pairing up for a short time. Even if they decay quickly, this leads to fluctuations of the Λ fields around the trivial saddle point. Thus, the coupling terms like $u_R^\dagger \Lambda u_L$ spontaneously comes into presence and disappears again. If there is a background, but no condensate, the fermion would pick up a tiny mass, but would not come to rest, i.e., they would show features a bit similar to neutrinos.

An investigation of such (purely hypothetic) fermions, which pick up mass only by fluctuations of the Λ fields would be an interesting project. As discussed they would come along with the light composite bosons. They would show a feature, which would distinguish such particles from others. Massless and massive particles are deflected differently in gravitational fields. For example, light is deflected by gravitating bodies by a different angle than matter. Particles, which obtain mass by Λ field fluctuations would lie somewhere in between. The effective central potential of a mass acting on a test mass differs for massive and massless test masses by the presence or absence of the Newtonian term [10, 11]. If mass is turned on and off by fluctuations, the effective potential would lie somewhere in between massive and massless. In other words, the effective gravitational potential for a fluctuating mass is weaker than for massive particles, but stronger than for light. Their orbits would be larger than for a regular massive particles caught by the potential at the same initial kinetic energy. In agglomerations of matter, where kinetic initial conditions would be similar for all particles, such particles would be more spread out. To put it to the extreme, in collisions between galaxies such particles should overshoot compared to the ordinary mass bulk due to their

⁸It might very well be that the presented technique does not have anything to do with the actual Higgs particle. It is just amusing to note that whenever there are bound states, potential terms and approximative Yukawa-like couplings emerge and do not have to be put in manually. For the question of the physical relevance of serious composite Higgs models, please see [9].

weaker deflection.⁹ The point is that their motion, but not their contribution to gravitation on other bodies or light, would be affected. This, of course, is purely hypothetical and should be taken with a grain of salt and a smile.

More promising is a study of known bound state systems like mesons and baryons using the new method. This would require several extension of the presented method, especially regarding the treatment of self-interactions of the gluon field. However, it would allow a comparison with experimental results and other already existing approaches.

8 Summary

I applied a method for treating bound states in quantum field theory [1] to the simplest and most generic constituent particles, Weyl fermions. The latter can be seen as building blocks for fermions richer in structure. I expect this to be applicable to a wide range of systems in high-energy physics and condensed matter physics. There is some notable structure emerging from expanding this theory, especially due to the non-linear parts not present in the original Bethe-Salpeter equation. While a bosonic spin singlet and triplet are expected upfront, there appear massive and massless modes and the path integral over degrees of freedom with vanishing kinetic term restricts massless modes to maximum spin configurations. The saddle point equation does not appear as a Klein-Gordon equation, but in a Schroedinger form. In the Gaussian effective action, the fields develop uncharged massive and charged massless components. Next steps would be a rigorous study for explicit choices of interactions and, more importantly, to experimentally accessible examples.

9 Appendix

9.1 Calculation of $\mathcal{G}^{(1)}$

I add a few notes on the calculation of

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)} &= i \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \left(G_{L,s'}^{-1}(\epsilon, \mathbf{k}) G_{R,s}^{-1}(\epsilon + \omega, \mathbf{p}) - |\Lambda_{ss'}|^2 \right)^{-1} \\
 &= i \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \frac{1}{(\epsilon + s'(k - i\eta))(\epsilon + \omega - s(p - i\eta)) - |\Lambda_{ss'}|^2} \\
 &= i \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \frac{1}{(\epsilon - a)(\epsilon - b) - c} .
 \end{aligned} \tag{111}$$

In the last step I have introduced the abbreviations

$$\begin{aligned}
 a &= -s'(k - i\eta) \\
 b &= -\omega + s(p - i\eta) \\
 c &= |\Lambda_{ss'}|^2 .
 \end{aligned} \tag{112}$$

Write the denominator of the integrand as

$$(\epsilon - a)(\epsilon - b) - c = (\epsilon - A)(\epsilon - B) \tag{113}$$

⁹Although this reminds a little of the dark matter maps via gravitational lensing, it should be stressed that the particles considered here would not strictly fulfill the $1/a^3$ definition of dark matter (with a being the scale factor) on average. (Although they would enter the dark matter balance somehow.) This formal distinction should keep me out of trouble.

with

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \frac{1}{2} \left(a + b + \sqrt{(a-b)^2 + 4c} \right), \\ B &= \frac{1}{2} \left(a + b - \sqrt{(a-b)^2 + 4c} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (114)$$

For later use, note that

$$A - B = \sqrt{(a-b)^2 + 4c}. \quad (115)$$

The first task is to identify the poles for the contour integration. For a finite c we can expand the square root (which may break down if we let $c \rightarrow 0$, but the result below still holds). There are two cases to distinguish:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \frac{1}{2} \left(-\omega + s(p-k) + \sqrt{(\omega - s(p+k))^2 + 4c + i s \eta \operatorname{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))} \right), \quad s = s' \\ A &= \frac{1}{2} \left(-\omega + s(p+k) + \sqrt{(\omega - s(p-k))^2 + 4c} - 2i s \eta \right), \quad s' = -s. \end{aligned} \quad (116)$$

Analogously,

$$\begin{aligned} B &= \frac{1}{2} \left(-\omega + s(p-k) - \sqrt{(\omega - s(p+k))^2 + 4c - i s \eta \operatorname{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))} \right), \quad s = s' \\ B &= \frac{1}{2} \left(-\omega + s(p+k) - \sqrt{(\omega - s(p-k))^2 + 4c} - 2i s \eta \right), \quad s' = -s. \end{aligned} \quad (117)$$

We see that like in the 'massless' case, i.e., with the trivial saddle point (here this would be $c = 0$), the poles of A and B are on the same side if $s' = -s$. In this case the integral vanishes.

Let's close the contour such that the pole at A is picked up, i.e., in the upper half plane with a factor $2\pi i$ if $s \cdot \operatorname{sign}(\omega - s(p+k)) = 1$ and in the lower half plane with a factor $-2\pi i$ if $s \cdot \operatorname{sign}(\omega - s(p+k)) = -1$. More explicitly,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)}(\omega, \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p}) &= i \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \frac{1}{(\epsilon - A)(\epsilon - B)} \\ &= -\frac{s\delta_{ss'} \operatorname{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))}{A - B}. \end{aligned} \quad (118)$$

Inserting A and B , this becomes

$$\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)}(\omega, \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p}) = -\frac{s\delta_{ss'} \operatorname{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))}{\sqrt{(\omega - s(p+k))^2 + 4|\Lambda_{ss'}|^2 + i s \eta \operatorname{sign}(\omega - s(p+k))}}. \quad (119)$$

The square root of sums of squares indicates a level repulsion near zero energy and the opening of a gap.

9.2 Calculation of $\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(2)}$

The second order expansion kernel reads

$$\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(2)} = \frac{i}{2} \operatorname{Tr}' \frac{1}{((\epsilon + s'k)(\epsilon + \omega - sp) - |\Lambda_{ss'}|^2)^2}. \quad (120)$$

Like before, write

$$\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(2)} = \frac{i}{2} \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \frac{1}{[(\epsilon - a)(\epsilon - b) - c]^2} = \frac{i}{2} \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \frac{1}{[(\epsilon - A)(\epsilon - B)]^2} \quad (121)$$

with the same abbreviations as in the calculation of $\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)}$. The poles lie in the same half planes as before, so we can immediately evaluate the integral using the residue theorem for multiple poles. The resulting additional prefactor is 1/2 times -2 , i.e., just an overall minus sign compared to the first order term. Thus

$$\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{s\delta_{ss'}}{(A - B)^3} \text{sign}(\omega - s(p + k)) \quad (122)$$

or explicitly

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(2)}(\omega, \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p}) &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)}(\omega, \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p})}{(\omega - s(p + k))^2 + 4|\Lambda_{ss'}|^2 + is\eta \text{sign}(\omega - s(p + k))} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{s\delta_{ss'} \text{sign}(\omega - s(p + k))}{[(\omega - s(p + k))^2 + 4|\Lambda_{ss'}|^2]^{3/2} + is\eta \text{sign}(\omega - s(p + k))}. \end{aligned} \quad (123)$$

The second order kernel $\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(2)}$ comes with opposite sign than $\mathcal{G}_{ss'}^{(1)}$.

9.3 Quadratic order in tensor representation

The quadratic order terms can easily be transformed into the tensor product representation, formally just replacing the fields by their "tilde" counterparts. Then,

$$i\text{Tr}\{G_L \Lambda^\dagger G_R \Lambda\} = \text{Tr}\{\tilde{\Lambda}^\dagger (iG_R \otimes G_L^T) \tilde{\Lambda}\}. \quad (124)$$

This is a simple alternative to express the Gaussian theory, while for the fourth order it is much less convenient. Now define

$$\mathcal{G} := iG_R \otimes G_L^T. \quad (125)$$

With the charge conjugation operator $\mathcal{C}_L = i\mathbb{1} \otimes \sigma_2$ we can write

$$\begin{aligned} i\text{Tr}\{G_L \Lambda^\dagger G_R \Lambda\} &= \text{Tr}\{\tilde{\Lambda}^\dagger \mathcal{C}_L^\dagger \mathcal{C}_L (iG_R \otimes G_L^T) \mathcal{C}_L^{-1} \mathcal{C}_L \tilde{\Lambda}\} \\ &= \text{Tr}\{(\tilde{\Lambda}')^\dagger (iG_R \otimes G_L) \tilde{\Lambda}'\} \\ &= \text{Tr}\{(\tilde{\Lambda}')^\dagger \tilde{\mathcal{G}} \tilde{\Lambda}'\}, \end{aligned} \quad (126)$$

where

$$\tilde{\Lambda}' = \mathcal{C}_L \tilde{\Lambda} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Lambda_{11} \\ \Lambda_{12} \\ \Lambda_{21} \\ \Lambda_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad (127)$$

such that

$$\tilde{\Lambda}' = \begin{pmatrix} \Lambda_{12} \\ -\Lambda_{11} \\ \Lambda_{22} \\ -\Lambda_{21} \end{pmatrix} \quad (128)$$

The terms involving Q can also be transformed using $\tilde{Q}' := \mathcal{C}_L \tilde{Q}$. In quadratic order we can formally integrate out the $\tilde{\Lambda}'$ fields and get a nice 'Schroedinger' type equation. However, the inversion of the Green operator is only straightforward after additional projections on positive and negative energy solutions. The calculation, using the single time argument approach, yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \tilde{\mathcal{G}}(\omega, \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}') \\ &= \int (d^3 p) e^{i\mathbf{p} \cdot (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')} \int (d^3 k) e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{y}' - \mathbf{y})} \\ & \quad \left\{ \frac{\Pi_{R,+}(\mathbf{p}) \otimes \Pi_{L,+}(\mathbf{k}) - \Pi_{R,-}(\mathbf{p}) \otimes \Pi_{L,-}(\mathbf{k})}{\omega - (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_R \otimes \mathbb{1}) \cdot \mathbf{p} - (\mathbb{1} \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma}_L) \cdot \mathbf{k}} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (129)$$

with projectors

$$\Pi_{R/L,\pm}(\mathbf{p}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 \pm \frac{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{R/L} \cdot \mathbf{p}}{p} \right). \quad (130)$$

Here, $p = |\mathbf{p}|$.

This points towards a decomposition into positive and negative energy components. Define the fields

$$\lambda(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}) = \begin{pmatrix} \Pi_{R,+}(\mathbf{p}) \otimes \Pi_{L,+}(\mathbf{k}) \tilde{\Lambda}' \\ \Pi_{R,+}(\mathbf{p}) \otimes \Pi_{L,-}(\mathbf{k}) \tilde{\Lambda}' \\ \Pi_{R,-}(\mathbf{p}) \otimes \Pi_{L,+}(\mathbf{k}) \tilde{\Lambda}' \\ \Pi_{R,-}(\mathbf{p}) \otimes \Pi_{L,-}(\mathbf{k}) \tilde{\Lambda}' \end{pmatrix} \quad (131)$$

and its conjugate counterpart. For the components '+-' and '-+' the Green function has zeros. This means that integrating out these components with only the linear term coupling them to Q leads to a functional δ function for the corresponding Q field components. This leaves us with two components and we can write

$$\lambda(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}) = \begin{pmatrix} \Pi_{R,+}(\mathbf{p}) \otimes \Pi_{L,+}(\mathbf{k}) \tilde{\Lambda}' \\ \Pi_{R,-}(\mathbf{p}) \otimes \Pi_{L,-}(\mathbf{k}) \tilde{\Lambda}' \end{pmatrix}. \quad (132)$$

Then the Green function can be written

$$\mathcal{G}_0(\omega, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}) = \frac{1}{\omega - (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_R \otimes \mathbb{1}) \cdot \mathbf{p} - (\mathbb{1} \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma}_L) \cdot \mathbf{k}} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{1} & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathbb{1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (133)$$

The Gaussian path integral for the Λ fields yields an action

$$S_{\text{eff}} = \text{Tr} \bar{Q}' [i\partial_t - \mathcal{H}_0 - V'] Q' \quad (134)$$

with $\bar{Q}' = (Q')^\dagger \beta$ and

$$\mathcal{H}_0(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}) = (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_R \otimes \mathbb{1}) \cdot \mathbf{p} + (\mathbb{1} \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma}_L) \cdot \mathbf{k}. \quad (135)$$

The saddle point equation in quadratic order is of the Schroedinger type

$$i\partial_t Q' = [\mathcal{H}_0 + V'] Q'. \quad (136)$$

Here

$$V' = \beta \mathcal{C}_L V \mathcal{C}_L^{-1}. \quad (137)$$

The result is the Bethe-Salpeter equation in a Schroedinger form, in analogy to the original QED setting of the Bethe-Salpeter equation with instantaneous interaction, which comes with similar projectors [6, 7].

References

- [1] J. Rollbühler, Zenodo (2019). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2596127>
- [2] H. A. Bethe, E. E. Salpeter, Phys. Rev. **82**, 309 (1951), Phys. Rev. **84**, 1232 (1951). M. Gell-Mann, F. Low: Phys. Rev. **84**, 350 (1951).
- [3] B. Povh, K. Rith, C. Scholz, F. Zetsche, *Teilchen und Kerne*, Springer-Verlag Heidelberg (1997).
- [4] W. Greiner, *Relativistische Quantenmechanik*, Verlag Harry Deutsch (1987).
- [5] D. Tong, *Quantum Field Theory*, (2006), <http://www.damtp.cam.ac.uk/user/tong/qft.html>
- [6] E. E. Salpeter, Phys. Rev. **87**, 328 (1952).
- [7] W. Greiner, J. Reinhardt, *Quantenelektrodynamik*, Verlag Harry Deutsch (1995).
- [8] W. Greiner, B. Müller, *Eichtheorie der schwachen Wechselwirkung*, Verlag Harry Deutsch (1995).
- [9] P. A. Zyla et al. (Particle Data Group), Prog. Theor. Exp. Phys. 2020, 083C01 (2020) and 2021 update.
- [10] T. Fliessbach, *Allgemeine Relativitätstheorie*, Spektrum Akademischer Verlag, Heidelberg (1998).
- [11] J. Rollbühler, Zenodo (2020). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3732616>